

Further Studies on *Sarcococca Pruniformis* Lindl.

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In a previous communication¹, we reported the isolation of a minor alkaloid, saracodinine, m.p. 136°, and a neutral compound, m.p. 240-48°, from the leaves of *Sarcococca pruniformis* Lindl. On further investigation saracodinine is shown to have structure (I) and the neutral component, (III).

The base, saracodinine, crystallises from acetone in fine needles, m.p. 136°, the elementary analysis of which indicates the empirical formula, $C_{23}H_{32}N_2$ (M.W. 342). It exhibits a characteristic UV absorption at 250 m μ (heteroannular diene). The IR spectrum exhibits peaks for : C.Me (7.35 μ) and N.Me (7.12 μ). The most abundant peak in its mass spectrum appears at m/e 72, which is most probably due to Me-CH=N⁺ Me₂ as observed in 20-dimethylaminopregnane derivative².

The alkaloid on catalytic hydrogenation in glacial acetic acid with the Adams catalyst forms tetrahydro-saracodinine, $C_{23}H_{42}N_2$, m.p. 144-45°, which is found to be identical with chonemorphine³ (IIa), m.p. 145-46°, by mixed m.p. determination and from superimposable IR spectra. Tetrahydro-saracodinine on methylation with formic acid and formaldehyde furnishes *NN*-dimethylchonemorphine⁴ (IIb), m.p. 108-109°. These conversion experiments with saracodinine and its UV spectrum establish the structure of the alkaloid as 3-amino-20- α -dimethylamino- Δ^3 , Δ^5 -pregnadiene (I).

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This heteroannular diene structure has been corroborated by mass spectra, the details of which will be published elsewhere.

The possibility of the imino structure of saracodinine, which may exist in equilibrium with the amine form (I), has been considered and further experimental work to secure direct evidence for the presence of imino form of saracodinine is under way.

The neutral compound, $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$ (M.W. 442), m.p. 246-48°, responds positive to the test for triterpene. Its IR spectrum in chloroform discloses presence of -OH group at 2.85 μ . On acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine, it forms a diacetyl derivative, $C_{30}H_{48}(OCOCH_3)_2$, m.p. 217-18°. The mass spectrum of the original compound showed intense peaks at M-31 (-CH₂OH) and M-18 (H₂O), besides the molecular ion peak at m/e 442. These spectral measurements and other physical and chemical properties of the compound suggest its identity with betulin⁵⁻⁷ (III), which has subsequently been confirmed from a direct comparison of their IR spectra and from their mixed m.p. determinations.

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